

**Settlement of *Perna perna* larvae in successful and unsuccessful rehabilitation sites
in Coffee Bay**

By

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Abstract

Settlement is a major determinant of intertidal organisms. Arrival and attachment on suitable substrata are essential requirements for species survival. Populations of the brown mussel *Perna perna* in the former Transkei have been reported to be depleted through over exploitation by subsistence harvesters. This is a problem because recovery after disturbance is very slow. There is a Mussel Rehabilitation Project in Coffee Bay which attaches mussels onto the rocks for rehabilitation and rehabilitation is considered as successful in some sites and unsuccessful in some sites. The study examined the effect of settlement of Brown mussel *Perna perna* larvae in successful and unsuccessful sites for rehabilitation. Brown mussel larvae settlement was monitored at 6 sites in Coffee Bay situated between Hole in the Wall and Umtata River mouth in the Eastern Cape, S.A. Each site had 6 artificial larvae collectors about 30cm apart. Larvae collectors were replaced fortnightly from May to September during spring low tide. Larvae abundance showed varying picks among sites, with high picks observed in successful sites for rehabilitation. There was a positive correlation between larvae settlement and rehabilitation success of brown mussels in Coffee Bay. The amount of larvae settlement was higher in successful sites than in unsuccessful sites. According to the MRP staff Nqutheni was the best site for rehabilitation and that was based on the rehabilitation success. However, in this study Ocean was the site with higher number of larvae settling. These results indicate that delivery of larvae in these sites is different, with some sites receiving more larvae than others. In conclusion, the effect of aspect on settlement highlights the importance in successful site selection, suggesting that mussel larvae settlement has an effect on mussel rehabilitation in Coffee Bay.

Keywords: *Perna perna*, Larvae, Settlement, Rehabilitation,

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1. INTRODUCTION

Brown mussel *Perna perna* is native to tropical and subtropical regions. *Perna perna* is the dominant species on the rocky shores of the south, east and west coast of southern Africa (Berry 1978; Schurink & Griffiths 1990) and has become invasive in the Gulf of Mexico and Newzealand (Hicks *et al.*1999).

P. perna is a relatively elongated, low shelled bivalve that occurs naturally (van Erkom Schurink & Griffiths 1991). The best identifying character of *P. perna* is an internal “divided posterior retractor mussel scar” and can also be easily recognized externally by its brown color (van Erkom Schurink & Griffiths 1991). The shell of *P.perna* is thin around the edges and thickens posteriorly (Salaya 1973). The resillial ridge of the mussel is pitted, unlike other bivalve species (van Erkom Schurink & Griffiths 1991).

The shape of the larvae is assessed in terms of the prominence of the umbos, the outline of the shell, its convexity and the ratio between length and height (Bayne 1976). In mytilid larvae, the anterior shell margin is narrow and the posterior margin is broader and is often extended vertically (Bayne 1976).

P. perna has two separate sexes that can be recognized during the breeding season by the mantle color (Lasiak & Barnard 1995). Mussels reproduce through external fertilization; they release sperm and eggs into the water column (Bayne 1976). Mussels invest enormous amount of energy in reproductive processes, however the total energy available to each individual is limited, and those processes involve, external fertilization, long-lived larval dispersal and final settlement (Bayne 1976).

In Natal, South Africa, Berry (1978) reported that there are two spawning periods between May and October, however sometimes spawning may extend till December. In contrast, van Erkom Schurink and Griffiths (1991) found a “single prolonged spawning season” to exist based on the presence of the spawning activity in each month. In Transkei, breeding season is extended from April to September with minor spawning events that occur from December to February (Lasiak 1986).

According to (Bayne 1976) after fertilization, the larva develops into a Trocophore before secretion of the shell. The first larval shell prodissoconch I, is secreted by the shell gland of Veliger (Bayne 1976). The larva is now at the straight hinge or D-shaped hinges (Rees 1950). In this stage the larva has thin transparent shell with no growing lines; however has a ciliate velum that emerges from the valve while it swims (Carriker 1961). The velum is the most distinctive organ of the larvae (Carriker 1961).

The second stage, Veliconcha is marked by disintegration of the second larval shell, called Prodissoconch II (Rees 1950). This stage is distinguished by the emergence of umbos above the hinge line on both valves (Rees 1950). The Pediveliger stage as proposed by (Carriker 1961) shows umbos projecting above the hinge line and growing wrinkles in the valves. This stage is distinguished by velum, functional foot and by the appearance of the ocellus-like spots on the center of each valve (Carriker 1961). After metamorphosis, adult shell is secreted and dissoconch begins, and the young post larva is called a plantigrade (Carriker 1961).

Plantigrades or larvae return to the shore through settlement, which is one of the main processes regulating the dynamics and structure of intertidal populations (Roughgarden *et*

al. 1988). Settlement is the permanent, reversible or irreversible contact that the larvae establish with the substratum (Bayne 1964; Keough & Downes 1982).

One of the most important aspects of mussel life styles is their ability to secrete strong byssal threads and attach to variety of substrates (Alfaro *et al.* 2004). Byssal threads are produced throughout mussel's lifetime, they provide a certain level of mobility and control throughout primary and secondary settlement phases (Alfaro & Jeff 2002).

During primary settlement phase, juveniles or plantigrades may settle on filamentous algae and hydroids with thin byssal threads (Alfaro *et al.* 2004). Juveniles are highly mobile and selective of their settlement substratum (Seed & Richardson 1999; Alfaro & Jeff 2002; Alfaro 2005). Byssal attachment may be of particular importance in the early life of mussels, attachment and re-attachment continue throughout the secondary phase (Moreno 1995).

In secondary phase plantigrade may attach to, and detach on several substrata prior selecting sites of permanent attachment on established mussel beds (Suchanek 1985). Mussel beds form a packed matrix that decreases the effect of wave action, temperature and sunlight (Suchanek 1985). Mussel gathering increases the amount of habitat suitable for other organisms by modifying the substratum (Suchanek 1985; Seed *et al.* 2000). As a result mussels can be considered to be “physical ecosystem engineers” (Jones *et al.* 1997). Nonetheless, complete detachment once juveniles become adults is less likely (Tan 1975).

Mussels are exploited as food throughout the world; however in southern Africa this resource is especially important, since mussels form over 80% of harvested intertidal

animals and the main source of protein for local communities (Lasiak & Field 1995). According to Lasiak and Dye (1989) the tradition of subsistence of mussel harvesting is very strong. As a result population of *P.perna* has been over-exploited on many shores and mussel population has declined in the last few decades (Lasiak & Dye 1989; Harris *et al* 1998). Dye and Dyantyi (2002) developed a technique to artificially rehabilitate over-exploited mussel beds. This technique is being used by a MRP (Mussel Rehabilitation Project) in Coffee Bay. This project was initiated by researchers from WSU and local community. Experience of the MRP staff has shown that some sites are extremely successful for rehabilitation (reaching over 80% mussel cover in less than a year) Pers. Com. Whilst rehabilitation is unsuccessful in other sites (some sites have been abandoned after trying to rehabilitate them for a year and reaching only 5% mussel cover) Pers.comm (Calvo-Ugarteburu)

In order to replicate the Mussel Rehabilitation Project at a larger scale in other denuded areas it is important in enabling selection of successful rehabilitation sites. One possible reason for the differential success is the amount of settlement occurring in each site. Thus this project is aiming at quantifying the mussel settlement at sites considered as successful and unsuccessful for rehabilitation, and to establish whether there is a relationship between rehabilitation success and mussel larvae settlement.

Marine intertidal populations and assemblages owe much of their complexity and variability to several biotic and abiotic factors operating at widely ranging spatial and temporal scales (Charles *et. al* 2008). Among the factors larval supply can strongly affect intertidal assemblages. These factors include topography which has an important effect

on near shore oceanography, larval transport, settlement and adult distribution of benthic organisms (Charles *et. al* 2008).

2. HYPOTHESIS

H_0 = there is no difference in larvae settlement between successful and unsuccessful rehabilitation sites

$H_A \neq$ there is a difference in larvae settlement between successful and unsuccessful rehabilitation sites

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 FIELD LOCATION

The study was carried out on the exposed rocky shores in Coffee Bay, between the Hole in the Wall and Umtata River mouth in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa. Six sites were selected with the help of the Mussel Rehabilitation Project (MRP) staff: three sites (Ocean S 31° 58' 45.5" E 29° 09' 20.4", Rhini S 31° 48' 28.5" E 29° 09' 39.4" and Nqutheni S 29° 8' 51" E 32° 0' 12.42") were regarded as successful for rehabilitation, and the other three sites (Mthini S 31° 57' 20.6" E 29° 11' 01.6", Lwandlana S 31° 58' 39.2" E 29° 09' 43.6" and Hlungulwana S 29° 9' 53" E 32° 3' 13.34") were regarded as unsuccessful for rehabilitation.

Fig. 1. Selected study sites along the coast in Coffee Bay: 1: Mthini, 2: Rhini, 3: Lwandlana, 4: Ocean, 5: Nqutheni and 6: Hlungulwana.

3.2 FIELD METHODS

Mussel settlement was monitored once a month between May and September 2009 during spring low tide. Plastic scouring pads (diameter 10-11cm, thickness 2cm) were used as settler collectors (Porri *et al.* 2006). Six holes were drilled at each site using a HILTI TE 7-A drill with size 10 drill bit, and 6 nylon plugs (10mm x 50mm) were inserted in each hole. One bolt was screwed in each hole, and a scouring pad was tied onto each eye bolt using three cable ties (DIM 198 x4.7mm). After a fortnight, the plastic

scouring pads were removed, each was placed in a plastic bottle, and six new scouring pads were tied on the same eye bolts pads. On some occasions scouring pads were lost due to high wave action especially in the sites that are regarded as successful. Each of the plastic bottles with collected plastic scouring pads samples were filled with 70% alcohol for preservation. Samples were taken to the laboratory for processing. Only 3 scouring pads were analyzed per month.

3.3 PROCESSING OF SCOURING PADS

9ml of bleach were added to each plastic bottle closed and shaken for 5 minutes. After 5 minutes the scouring pads were retrieved from the bottle and placed into a bucket.

The contents of the samples were poured into the bucket through a 75 μ m sieve and the plastic container was rinsed thoroughly using running water. The elastic bands keeping the scouring pads intact were cut and rinsed in the same bucket. The scouring pads were unrolled, opened and rinsed several times in the bucket, removing every little sediment or detritus off the plastic scouring pad using running water. Water from the bucket was poured through the 75 μ m sieve. It was necessary to lift the sieve slightly to allow water flow in it. Rinsing of the scouring pads was done repeatedly until the scouring pads appeared clean with no trace of sediment or detritus left. After rinsing, the scouring pads were hanged on the sink to dry, and again were observed under a dissecting microscope to verify that no settler or recruit remained attached to the scouring pad. The labels were also rinsed over 75 μ m sieve using running water. Sample information was recorded from the sample label.

All the sample contents were collected in a Petri dish and examined under a dissecting microscope at 32x (Porri *et al.* 2006). *Perna perna* settlers were identified, measured to the nearest 0.01mm and were counted (F. Porri, Pers com).

3.4. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis was performed using a two-way ANOVA to analyze the effect of sites and months on larvae settlement. Spearman rank correlation test was also performed to determine whether there is correlation between larvae settlement and rehabilitation status.

4. RESULTS

Table1. 2-way ANOVA on the effect of sites and months on larvae settlement.

Source of variation	SS	Degrees of freedom	MS	F	P
Month	8317.95	4	2079.49	78.321	0.000000
Site	2017.93	5	403.59	15.2005	0.000000
Month*site	1291.05	20	64.55	2.4313	0.004368
Error	1566.5	59	26.55		

Sites were significantly different ($p=0.000000$) and months were also significantly different ($p=0.000000$). Both months and sites showed a significant effect on larvae

settlement and the interaction between months and sites also showed a significant difference with ($p=0.004368$).

Table 2. Ranked sites according to rehabilitation success based on MRP data.

Rank	Sites ranked according to rehabilitations success %	Sites
1	71.5	Nqutheni
2	54.6	Ocean
3	27.5	Rhini
4	5.6	Hlungulwana
5	2.3	Lwandlana
6	0.1	Mthini

MRP data showed that Nqutheni had highest percentage cover of mussels, while Mthini had the lowest.

All the sites were ranked from 1-6 according to rehabilitation success. Spearman's rank correlation showed that there is a correlation between rehabilitation success and larvae settlement ($p=0.66$).

Table 3. Sites arranged according to the degree of larvae availability from the highest to the lowest number of larval settlement.

Amount of settlement	Site	Rehabilitation
Highest	Ocean	Successful
Higher	Nqutheni	Successful
High	Rhini	Successful
Low	Hlungulwana	Unsuccessful
Lower	Mthini	Unsuccessful
Lowest	Lwandlana	Unsuccessful

The amount of larvae settling was relatively the highest in Ocean, while MRP staff considered Nqutheni as the best site for rehabilitation. Moreover, the MRP data also showed that Mthini was ranked number 6, while in the study the lowest site according to the availability of larvae was Lwandlana.

Fig. 2. Average number of *P. perna* larvae in unsuccessful and successful sites during the sampling period.

Mussel spawning occurred in May and the spats were still too small in the first stage of development, this is why settling of larvae was more abundant in July. That was the month where there was more developed larvae and at that time there was more larvae settling on substrata (Plastic scouring pads).

Similar patterns of larvae settlement were observed at all six sites, successful and unsuccessful, with main peaks in July. Variability in larvae numbers was significantly affected by the interaction between fortnights and sites. During the sampling period it is clearly shown that larvae numbers differed considerably between sites, but peak of abundance appeared at all sites in July, consequently, successful sites showed strong peaks, while unsuccessful sites showed weaker peaks. This highlighted that the average numbers of larvae found during sampling period were considerable variable from May to September as well as from one site to another.

5. DISCUSSION

Numerous studies done on the settlement of benthic marine invertebrates indicate spatial and temporal variability over a wide range of scales (Porri *et al.* 2008). Spatial variability occurs among geographic locations, among sites within shores, while temporal variation occurs on scales of days, weeks, months and years (Porri *et al.* 2008).

The results showed that settlement of *P. perna* larvae varies over spatial and temporal scales and that is greatly influenced by various factors that affect variation of larvae settlement, these factors include seasonality of the reproduction, hydrodynamics, water temperature, geography and topography (Porri *et al.* 2006). According to Porri *et al.* (2006), temporal variation in larval availability is very important apart from long-term (e.g. seasonal) variation; abundance in the water column can change dramatically (e.g. seconds, hours, days, and week). The patterns of the larvae during the study were generally the same inspite of the variability resulting in significant interactions and clear overall trends for the study period.

This study showed differences in settlement rates over months and that was visible by the total number of larvae that were collected from each site in a period of a fortnight. Caceres *et al.* (1994) found that mussel settlers do not initially show active substratum selection, but tend to stay on the substratum they first encounter through random collisions, and that wave action can control settlement through subsequent mechanical dislodgement.

The total number of larvae was higher at Ocean compared to all other sites irrespective of whether they were successful or not, and according to Mcquaid & Lindsay (2000), barnacles in particular have shown that certain areas can experience lower settlement than others due to their larval availability (lower densities of larvae in the water column adjacent to the shore). In this study it was clearly shown that the larvae was more abundant on successful sites. The effect of sites on settler abundance indicates differential delivery of larvae to the shore. Porri *et al.* (2006) found that larvae are preferentially transported to some sites rather than others. Explanation for what Porri *et al.* 2006 found was visible in this study, by the total larval availability recorded at each site during the study period.

In this study all settler collectors in successful sites (Nqutheni, Rhini and Ocean) were attached \pm 3meters away from the adult mussel beds. The same was done in unsuccessful sites even though the mussel cover was very little. Larval availability and settlement are among parameters with crucial biological importance for the regulation of spatial and temporal distribution and abundance of marine mussel populations (Porri *et al.* 2006).

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Larval availability and settlement are among those parameters with crucial biological importance for the distribution and abundance of mussel populations. The results of this study suggest that larvae are transported in all the sites, but survival is more to certain locations (successful sites) than others (unsuccessful sites). Since rates of larval settlement were varying throughout the study, it appears that settlement is likely to be a primary process in shaping of these mussel communities. All factors that have significant effect on the arrival of larvae are important in understanding and developing mussel population dynamics in Coffee Bay. Mussel larvae settlement was higher in sites that were considered successful for rehabilitation and there was correlation between Larvae settlement and rehabilitation status even though it was not strong. MRP should select sites according to the amount of larvae settlement for rehabilitation in Coffee Bay.

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